

NON-SYCRETISM OF THE NAQSHBANDI SUFIS

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Abstract

After four centuries (1200-1600 CE) of contact both the Hindus and Muslims in India had developed some common syncretic religious practices borrowed from each other. The fifth Mughal Emperor Akbar (1556-1605) in order to develop a religio-political common ground for all the different identities inhabiting his realm started promoting some beliefs and practices which are considered antithetical to the tenets of orthodox Sunni Islam. Many Sufi orders like the Chishti Silsila also believed in this type of tolerance. But it was the Naqshbandi Silsila which provided Sheikh Ahmed Sirhindi the ideological foundation to mount an opposition to these syncretic tendencies. This paper aims to examine critically the origins and impact of this ideology of non-syncretism.

Keywords : Naqshbandi, Sufi Silsila, Sheikh Ahmed Sirhindi, syncretism, Din-i-Ilahi, Tauhid-i-Ilahi, Wahdat-ul-Wajood, Wahdat-ush-Shuhood

INTRODUCTION

Different Muslim ethnicities like Turks, Afghans and Turco-Mongols from Western and Central Asia ruled the major part of the Hindu-majority subcontinent for nearly eight centuries. This necessitated a co-operative attitude to a certain extent at the grassroot level. The mystic form of Islam, Sufism provided the soft approach which could establish the religion in the land through a process of interaction with the local population. A state with Muslims as the ruling class was almost a guarantee against state persecution of the Sufis. Although there have been examples of Sufis enjoying state patronage in India, they largely distanced themselves from the activities and ideologies of the Ghazis (Muslim soldiers who fight against non-Muslims), the Sultans & Badshahs (Muslim rulers) and their supporting Ulema (Islamic scholars).

After the Ghurid conquest there was a considerable influx of Sufi saints into India. The Mongol invasion of the Muslim world accelerated the process. These saints learned the local language and preached tolerance and love for humanity. The tactical purpose behind this has been suggested. This might have been to familiarise the local people with Islam.¹ They didn't

practice social exclusion and their Khanqahs (hospices) were open to all people irrespective of their religion, caste, status etc. Hence, Hindus of all castes thronged to them and after the death of their Pir (spiritual master) they paid Ziyarat (homage) to their Dargahs (tomb shrines). The contacts between Chishtis and Hindu saints led the former to adopt practices like breathing exercises, Chilla-i-Makus (concentrating on God while suspended head down in a well for forty days and nights), offering water to new initiates, shaving heads etc.² Since these Sufis rarely prohibit any religious practice, the newly converted Indian Muslims didn't immediately do away with some of their old Hindu traditions. So, on the local level many syncretic practices were prevalent in the Indian society.

NAQSHBANDI SILSILA: TRANSOXIANA TO INDIA

The Naqshbandi Sufi Silsila also known as Silsila-i-Khawajagan (lit. Order of the masters) is said to have been founded by Khawaja Bahauddin Naqshband Bukhari (d. 1389), although some trace it to Khwaja Abu Yusuf Hamadani (d. 1140). Certainly, it was made popular in Transoxiana by Khwaja Bahauddin. Since this region was under the Chaghtai Khanate and later the Timurids, the Naqshbandi Sufis traditionally had relations with the Turco-Mongol rulers. The first Mughal Emperor of India, Babur's father Umar Sheikh Mirza of Ferghana was a follower of the Naqshbandi saint Khwaja Ubaidullah Ahrar. Ahrar's son was also revered by Babur. During the reign of Akbar many Naqshbandi saints migrated to India including Mirza Sharfuddin Hussain who was given the governorship of Ajmer and married to Akbar's sister Bakshi Banu Begum. Akbar's son Daniyal was also married to the daughter of a Naqshbandi saint.

The Naqshbandi Silsila in India received a boost after the arrival of Khwaja Baqi Billah Berang to Delhi from Kabul in 1563. Khwaja Baqi has been described as the source of all the later Muslim revivalist movements in the Indian subcontinent.³ He brought Ahmad Faruqi Sirhindi, an erudite scholar from the lineage of Caliph Umar, under his tutelage and made him his Khalifa (successor) in 1600 when Sirhindi was twenty-six years of age. The efforts to reform Islam has earned Sheikh Ahmad Sirhindi the title 'Mujaddid-i-Alf-i-Thani' (lit. Reformer of the Second Millennium). It is his spiritual lineage known as the Mujaddidiya which spread as far as Anatolia, Central Asia, Indonesia etc. It must be noted that Sirhindi had a brief stay at Agra in 1582 where he got into debates with the brothers Abul Fazal and Faizi,⁴ the former being

the main architect of Akbar's political ideology. Sheikh Yaqoob Sarfi Kashmiri was also a deep impression on Sirhindi's young mind as far as his anti-shiite views are concerned.⁵

ANTI-SYNCRETISM ORIGINS

The non-syncretic views of the pre-Mujaddidiya Naqshbandis became manifest during the political expression of their anti-Shiite identity during the Safavid oppression of the Sunnis.⁶ However, Ibn-ul Arabi's ideology of Wahdat-ul-Wajood (lit. Unity of Existence) was not considered against the Sharia by Naqshbandis like Abdul Rahman Jami and Ubaidullah Ahrar.⁷ But the strictness and the tradition of prohibition and shunning was evident tracing back to Sheikh Bahauddin disassociated himself from vocal Zikr (lit. recitation). The emphasis on religious fidelity to the Sharia (lit. The Path) was always there.⁸ They criticized the ostentatious communal rituals of the other Tariqas and considered them 'inferior'. Practices within the ambit of Mujahadat like fasting, night vigils, ritual seclusion etc. were targeted. Visits to the tombs of saints was also considered as Bid'at (lit. Innovation). The militancy with which such practices were opposed often led the followers into physical attacks on the Sheikhs of other orders.⁹

SHEIKH AHMED SIRHINDI

The original contribution of Sheikh Ahmad Sirhindi lies in the philosophy of Wahdat-ush-Shuhood (lit. Unity of Perception).¹⁰ He considered that the experience of unity between the God and the world has no objective reality, but occurs only in the mind of the believer. He saw in this ideology the accretion of Hindu pantheism. Thus, he considered Wahdat-ul-Wajood to be against the dogmas of Islam.¹¹ Although the similarity between Vedanta and Wahdat-ul-Wajood has been noted¹² the possibility of the latter being inspired from the former has been rejected.¹³ As claimed by Sirhindi, many Indian Sufis with no theological background were not capable of comprehending the higher kind of experiential states properly. They appeared to be more in the influence of the local traditions. It has been suggested that the attitude of Indian Mujaddidiyah Sheikhs towards such practices was just because these were peculiar to the Hindu Bhakti and Yoga traditions.¹⁴ This reasoning gets support due to the evidence from other Mujaddidiyah orders. Such exclusive attitude is not seen in the Anatolian Mujaddidiyah tradition, followers of which engaged with other Sufi traditions and indulged in dance and poetry.¹⁵ This insistence of Sirhindi on purging the Muslims of such Bid'ats has been described as "reform sufism" and "reformist anti-sufism".¹⁶ However, Sirhindi doesn't seem to be too

militant towards the orders which used to practice such things and claims that although the Naqshbandis don't follow them, they respect them.¹⁷ It has been suggested that Sirhindi never preached social exclusion.¹⁸ One should refrain from dealing with the infidels unless absolutely necessary, and even then treat with them contempt.¹⁹ This approach is very different from later Mujaddidiyah Naqshbandis like Mirza Mazhar Jan-i-Janan and Sheikh Fazlur Rahman Ganjmuradabadi. Mirza Mazhar didn't shy away in explaining the tenets of Hinduism in consonance with those of Islam. He didn't consider Hindus' idolatry as Shirk (associating partners with God). Ganjmuradabadi equated Allah with Hindu terms like 'Parmeshwar' to signify the common beliefs in both the faiths. Thus it can't be said that Naqshbandis in India stayed strictly non-syncretic.

AKBAR'S SYNCRETISM AND SIRHINDI'S REACTION

The Mughal Emperor Akbar (1556-1605) took steps which sought to remove the status of Hindus as second-class citizens of the Empire. He married Rajput princesses, one of whom was never converted to Islam.²⁰ He abolished the pilgrimage tax in 1562 and abolished the Jaziya in 1564. It was his personal quest for finding the ultimate religious truth which is common to all the religious sects. So he adopted some beliefs and practices from Hinduism, Jainism, and Zoroastrianism. He thought that every religion had something good to offer and no single religion could claim Monopoly over the ultimate truth. To be more well acquainted with the other religions and to find a common ground between them he established the Ibadat Khana (lit. The House of Worship) in 1575. In 1578, the Ibadat khana was thrown open to the experts of all religions like Buddhism, Jainism and Hinduism. In 1582, all of these efforts culminated in to the idea of Tauhid-i-Ilahi (lit. Unity of God). A spiritual leadership programme Din-i-Ilahi (lit. Religion of God) was also founded, borrowing practices from different religions and enrolling initiates under Akbar himself. Such broad-based ideology also helped politically to rope-in the nobility of different backgrounds into a single thread of loyalty towards the throne. The formulators of the ideology of Tauhid-i-Ilahi were inspired from the concept of Wahdat-ul-Wajood. In the opinion of Sirhindi such scholars betrayed Akbar in fulfilling their responsibility fully.²¹ He considered them to be narrow-minded and world-seeking. Akbar view of Tauhid-i-Ilahi didn't consider anyone unbeliever because through all religious worships Allah is worshipped.²² But Sirhindi considered such syncretism to be heretical²³ since Islam and Kufr are mutually exclusive.²⁴ He considered all Hindus to be Kafirs (lit. Unbelievers) and

opposed Akbar's policy to remove Jaziya, a special poll tax on Hindus. He considered it to be important for the suppression and humiliation of the Hindus. He wrote letters to higher officials urging them to remove Hindus from high positions.

Sirhindi was imprisoned in 1619 by the orders of the Emperor Jahangir due to his outspoken criticism of Shias. According to Naqshbandi accounts, after year of imprisonment when the Sheikh was brought in front of the Emperor, the former placed the following demands: (i) abolition of the Sijda before the Emperor; (ii) permission to slaughter cows; (iii) cessation of Bid'ats and (iv) reparation of mosques and restoration of the offices of Qazi and Ihtisab.²⁵ Whether true or not, the desire to humiliate the Hindus feature regularly in the Naqshbandi accounts. Jahangir's Kangra campaign in 1621 and the subsequent smashing of idols and the ritual slaughter of cow in the presence of Sirhindi has been described as his influence over the Emperor.²⁶ In Kashmir, in the same year inter-marriage between a Hindu man and a Muslim woman was made forbidden by royal decree.

IMPACT OF NAQSHBANDI SILSILA

The impact of the Naqshbandi Silsila has been transnational.²⁷ Sirhindi's Khalifas after migrating to different regions of India spread the influence of Naqshbandi Silsila far and wide. The Mujaddidiyah was one of the major waves of the Indian brand of Sunni Islam on the central Islamic lands of the middle East.²⁸ But it must be kept in mind that in calling this brand Indian the emphasis is on the place of origin of the contribution rather than its relevance to the socio-cultural conditions characterizing the Indian Muslims. Most of the concerns that Sirhindi had were applicable to the Muslim community at large, rather than being towards the Indian Muslims specifically. Denunciations of Hinduism and Hindus can't be considered central to his thought. It is due to his advocacy of orthodoxy amidst an environment characterized by the forces of the new age (the second millennium) that his impact on the subsequent Muslim political thinkers and Islamic reformist movements has been considerable. Every shade of political thought that espoused the Muslim cause in India in any way seems to hold Sirhindi in high regard. Shah Waliullah Dehlavi, the inspiration behind the Deobandi movement was a Naqshbandi. Sirhindi had a direct influence on Shah Waliullah. More indirect influence was on the later movements aiming to position the Muslim community within the Colonial and Nationalist contexts. Fazlur Rahman Ganjmuradabadi's followers founded the Nadwatul Ulama at Kanpur in 1892.²⁹ The poet and political philosopher Mohammed Iqbal has paid glowing

tributes to Sheikh Ahmad Sirhindi.³⁰ For Iqbal the reason to hold Sirhindi in high regard was his refusal to bow down to political power (Jahangir) and being the guardian of the Indian Muslim community. Maulana Abul Kalam Azad attributed to Sirhindi the revival of Islam during the Mughal period.³¹

CONCLUSION

The development of the Naqshbandi Silsila in India coincided with the emergence of challenges within the Indian Muslim society.³² Sheikh Ahmad Sirhindi's reaction must be viewed in the context of the socio-cultural conditions prevailing in the period. One front was the social level where Hindus and Muslims were in contact for the last four hundred years. The other was political where the Emperor was indulging in practices and policies which were in contravention of the orthodox Islamic way of life, trying to promote Hindus and Hindu culture. Sirhindi seems to respect the Sufi saints who indulged in practices considered by him futile to understand the true essence of God and Islam. On the other hand, he takes a militant stand against the conscious syncretic ideology of the ruling classes and batted for a state policy of humiliation of the beliefs and practices of the non-Muslims. The impact of Sirhindi's non-syncretic ideology can be seen up till the Muslim revivalist and reformist movements of the modern period.

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